

Cybersecurity Threats in Remote Work Environments A Case Study in Sri Lanka

*Understanding Risks and Solutions for Secure Digital Workspaces
During the COVID-19 Pandemic*

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2022 – 2023

Section One: Title, objective, responsibilities

Title or working title of research project (in the form of a question, objective or hypothesis): Research project objectives (e.g., what is the question you want to answer? What do you want to learn how to do? What do you want to find out?): Introduction, Objective, Sub Objective(s), Research Questions and/or Hypothesis

Title

Cybersecurity threats to people who are working remotely in Sri Lanka

Introduction

What is remote working? Its working style allows workers to work outside the office environment. It is based on the concept that it is not necessary to work in a specific place.

Instead of traveling to an office every day to work from a fixed desk, remote workers can execute their projects and goals wherever possible. People have the flexibility to plan their days so that they can experience their professional and personal lives to the fullest and live in peaceful harmony.

In light of the widespread COVID-19 epidemic, the research is centered on the potential threats to cyber security that are posed by remote employees in Sri Lanka. For the purpose of this study, Western Papers Industries, Wind Vision Industries, and E Solutions by RNX have been chosen as the participating businesses. A Google form will be used to collect responses from remote workers, and those responses will then be analyzed for their present level of security. The findings will assist organizations and workers in remote locations in Sri Lanka in better understanding the cyber security risks associated with remote work and developing strategies to mitigate such risks.

The research will look into the dangers that are posed by the utilization of new software and technologies for the purpose of work and communication. The findings of the study will include recommendations for how the companies under investigation might further improve their safety procedures.

Objectives

- To identifying cybersecurity threats experienced by remote workers during the pandemic period.
- To understand the challenges remote workers face in protecting their personal and work-related information and to identify solutions for Cyber Security threats.
- To observe if the companies are providing their employees with the necessary training and education to protect against cyber-attacks while working remotely.
- To assess how well current safeguards protect against cyberattacks.

Aim

To understand the reasons behind the cyber security issues faced by remote workers in Sri Lanka and to identify possible solutions for these problems. And to provide recommendations for improving the companies' cyber security measures to protect their sensitive data and information.

Research question

How has the pandemic affected cyber security for remote workers in Sri Lanka?

Hypothesis

H₁ – lack of knowledge about how to be safe from cyber-attacks are causing an increase in hacking

H₀ – lack of knowledge about how to be safe from cyber-attacks aren't causing an increase in hacking.

Section Two: Reasons for choosing this research project

Reasons for choosing the project (e.g., links to other subjects you are studying, personal interest, future, knowledge/skills you want to improve, why the topic is important): Motivation, Research gap

The study project "Cybersecurity threats to those who work remotely in Sri Lanka" was chosen based on a number of different factors. First of all, cybersecurity has become a major worry for people all over the world in the past few years. Because technology is changing so quickly and more and more people use the internet for communication, data storage, and financial transactions, security is more important than ever. Also, because of the COVID-19 pandemic, a lot of people have had to work from home. As a result, a lot more people are working from home. This makes it even more important to understand the cybersecurity risks that come with working from home and find ways to reduce them.

Another thing that makes me want to keep working on this project is that I'm interested in the field of cybersecurity. I think it's fascinating that technology can make our lives easier, but I'm also aware of the risks that could come with more people using it. I want to learn more about these risks and how they can be avoided by doing research on the potential cybersecurity risks that people who work remotely in Sri Lanka might face.

I also think that this research project could help us learn more about cybersecurity, especially when it comes to working remotely. This project will fill in the research gaps in Sri Lanka's cybersecurity field, which hasn't been studied as deeply as in other countries. The results of this study will give people, organizations, and policymakers useful information and suggestions that will help make working remotely in Sri Lanka less dangerous.

In conclusion, I chose to do research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" because it is a topic that interests me, because I am passionate about information technology, and because I want to help the field of cybersecurity learn more. "Cybersecurity threats to Sri Lankans who work from home" is the name of the research project. I'm sure that by the end of this project, I'll not only have learned and gotten better at new things, but I'll have also taken an important step toward a successful career in information technology.

Section Three: Literature sources searched

Use of key literature sources to support your objective, Sub Objective, research question and/or hypothesis: Can include the Conceptual Framework

All of the information for this research came from research journals, research articles, different books, and blogs written by different people.

"New Technologies and Remote Work: A Study of Work-Family Conflict" (Park and Lee, 2016) looked at how web technologies affect the conflicts between work and family for remote workers. The authors found that the use of web technologies like video conferencing and instant messaging has made it easier for remote workers to find a good balance between work and family life.

"Cybersecurity risks to Remote Workers" talks about both working from home and cyberattacks. Team members' pandemic productivity was measured by a questionnaire. Cyber risks and the benefits of working from home were looked at in the study. The study says that COVID-19-driven remote work has led to more successful cyberattacks. Human error was the biggest threat to data security, so virtual desktop infrastructure was recommended to keep business running. The WFH staff had security amnesia and let themselves be tricked. The goal of the study was to reduce the cyber risks that teleworkers and their companies face. (James, 2020)

The future of work is changing, and for businesses to stay in business, they need to change with it. One way they can do this is by letting their employees work from home. Gallup says that the number of cyberattacks has gone up by 85% since the beginning of remote work in 2015. (Robison, 2022)

"A Study of Work-Life Balance: Web-Based Technologies and Remote Work" (Berg and Borg, 2004) - This study looked at how web technologies affect the work-life balance of people who work from home. The authors found that when remote workers used web technologies, they were better able to manage their time and work more efficiently, which led to a better balance between work and life.

The goal of the study was to find out how the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) affects cyber security when working remotely. Amin Dangheralou and Hamid Jahankhani, the study's authors, used a questionnaire to find out how team members felt about the topic. The study found that the goal of GDPR is to make sure that digital data protection rules are consistent and uniform across Europe and that all digital platforms that work in Europe follow these rules. The goal of the study was to evaluate and measure how GDPR affects how well cyber security works for remote workers. (Amin Dangheralou, Hamid Jahankhani, 2019)

Section Four: Activities and timescales

Activities to be conducted during the research project (e.g., research, development, analysis of ideas, writing, data collection, numerical analysis, tutor meetings, production of final outcome, evaluation, writing the report) and how long this will take:

Milestone	Propose completion data
Project Initiation	04/12/2022
Literature Review	06/12/2022
Research Design	15/12/2022
Data Collection	26/01/2023
Data Analysis	02/01/2023
Results	07/01/2023
Conclusions and Recommendations	12/01/2023
Final Report	20/01/2023
Project proposal Submission	24/01/2023

Section Five: Research approach and methodologies

Type of research approach and methodologies you are likely to use, and reasons for your choice: What your areas of research will cover: Research Onion; Sample Strategy/Method; Sample Size

Research onions

The research onion is a visual model that shows the different steps of a research study, from defining the research problem to presenting the results.

For my research project on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka," I'm likely to use a positivist, deductive, quantitative research approach and a single-method survey as the main way to collect data.

I chose a positivist research method because it lets me look at the relationship between variables in an objective way and figure out what causes what. This method is good for looking into cybersecurity threats because it gives a systematic way to look into the problem and get information that can be used in general.

Starting with a theory or hypothesis and then gathering data to test it is the deductive method of research. This method is good for my research project because it lets me figure out how the independent variables (cybersecurity threats) relate to the dependent variable (the impact of cybersecurity threats on remote workers in Sri Lanka).

I chose a quantitative research method because it is good for looking at numbers, drawing conclusions about populations from sample data, and making broad statements about the results. This method works well for my research project because it lets me figure out how big cybersecurity threats are and what effect they have on remote workers in Sri Lanka.

I'm most likely to use a survey as my main way to get information. Surveys are a good way to collect data for a quantitative research project because they are a standard way to get information from a large number of people. I chose a one-method survey because it gives me a consistent way to collect data and reduces the chance of bias.

For this research project, I plan to use a cross-sectional sample method to get information. This method collects data from participants at a single point in time. It can be used to study the relationship between variables in an environment that doesn't change. Statistical power analysis will be used to figure out the sample size for this research project. It will depend on the size of the population and the level of accuracy that is wanted.

In short, the best way to look into cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka is to use a positivist, deductive, quantitative research method with a single-method survey as the main way to collect data. Using a cross-sectional sampling method and a sample size that is based on a statistical power analysis will make sure that the results are true to the population and have enough power to find real differences.

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						5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	Proposal	2022-12-05	2022-12-10	6.0 d.	100.0%	[Green bar from day 5 to 10]																																			
2	Creating the survey	2022-12-11	2022-12-12	2.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 11 to 15]																									
3	CHAPTER 1	2022-12-13	2022-12-15	3.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 13 to 15]																									
4	CHAPTER 2	2022-12-16	2022-12-19	4.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 16 to 19]																									
5	CHAPTER 3	2022-12-20	2022-12-24	5.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 20 to 24]																									
6	CHAPTER 4	2022-12-27	2022-12-30	4.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 27 to 30]																									
7	Data gathering	2022-12-31	2023-01-02	3.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 31 to 02]																									
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9	CHAPTER 5	2023-01-05	2023-01-10	6.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 05 to 10]																									
10	Review of the proposal	2023-01-11	2023-01-12	2.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 11 to 12]																									
11	Review of the report	2023-01-12	2023-01-13	2.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 12 to 13]																									
12	Presenting	2023-01-14	2023-01-15	2.0 d.	100.0%											[Green bar from day 14 to 15]																									

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**Cybersecurity threats to people who are working
remotely in Sri Lanka**

By
J.K Bhanuka Perera

Submitted in accordance with the requirements for the
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Regards,

Bhanuka Perera

ABSTRACT

Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, more people are working from home. This has created new cybersecurity risks for both employees and businesses. The goal of this research is to find out which cyberattacks happen most often when people work from home in Sri Lanka and to create a security policy to protect business continuity. A questionnaire was used to find out how productive team members thought they were and to look into the cyber risks and benefits of working from home. The results show that human error is the biggest threat to the security of companies' data, with social engineers and "security amnesia" also playing a role. The study shows how important it is for businesses to put in place effective security measures to protect themselves from cyber threats and keep workers productive when they work from home.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

DV: Dependent Variable (An increase in hacking)

IVE1_AV: First Independent Variable average (poor education and lack of knowledge)

IVE2_AV: Second Independent Variable average (lack of training and proper practices)

IVE3_AV: Third Independent Variable average (poor infrastructure)

IV1_E1: First Independent Variable (poor education and lack of knowledge)

IV2_1: Second Independent Variable (lack of training and proper practices)

IV3_1: Third Independent Variable (poor infrastructure)

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CHAPTER 1 – INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

The latest COVID-19 pandemic has changed our daily routines. Many businesses have adopted remote work in response to the need to maintain social distancing and reduce the risk of virus transmission. Thanks to the spread of appropriate digital technology, there has been a huge increase in the number of people using the Internet to perform their tasks remotely. Unfortunately, the risk of cyber-attacks increases with the proliferation of digital technology. In light of the recent COVID-19 pandemic in Sri Lanka, this research looks specifically at the cyber security risks posed by its remote workers.

The expansion of the digital economy and increased reliance on the Internet for jobs has resulted in new cybersecurity dangers for remote workers. Cybercriminals can more easily target remote workers depending on the nature of their work. The COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated these dangers, as hackers have used the fear and uncertainty created by the outbreak to target telecoms. More people are using their own devices at work, which may introduce new security threats because company-issued devices may not be as secure.

Cybersecurity risks can have serious consequences for remote workers, including financial loss and identity theft. Cyber-attacks not only affect individuals, but also have the potential to damage an organization's reputation and productivity. Thus, it is critical that remote workers recognize the dangers and take steps to protect themselves from cyber-attacks. In light of the country's improving economic situation and rapid technological development, more and more people in Sri Lanka are choosing to work from home, they open themselves up to a wider range of cyber risks. Phishing schemes, virus assaults, and identity theft are just a few examples of the many types of cyber risks that exist today. It is easier for cybercriminals to exploit vulnerabilities and steal sensitive information from a remote work environment and their companies because of the lack of both cyber and physical security measures.

Those working remotely in Sri Lanka need to be aware of the cybersecurity risks they face. With this study, we hope to better understand the unique cybersecurity threats faced by Sri Lanka's remote workforce and to provide solutions to mitigate such threats. Data from remote workers will be gathered via google form, and the present security measures will be analyzed. This study's findings will help policymakers, businesses, and telecommuting workers in Sri Lanka better understand the cybersecurity threats they face and take precautions to protect themselves.

Selected companies

Western papers - Western Papers Industries (Pvt) Ltd, an island-wide supplier of quality leaflets, was founded in 1998 by MIT graduate Shelton Perera. There are about 20 branches located in different parts of the island. It is a successful company with many achievements and has been able to win the trust of customers throughout its excellent service over the past 24 years. The head office that maintains all documents is located in Negombo, Sri Lanka. Before the pandemic company used its own systems complete their tasks and it was windows-based system only. But when it comes to remote working with the pandemic situation and having to work remotely the company has changed the system for a Web Based systems.

The company had to communicate its ideas, edit documents, hold meetings, and share various Data and information. The Company had to use other software and websites that they had never used before to achieve those goals and complete their daily tasks. By using new technologies and software as their means of communication, the company's sensitive data and information can be exposed to the outside world, thereby exposing the company to greater risks, so this project is to investigate cyber security risks in remote work.

Wind Vision - Wind Vision Industries (Pvt) Ltd, an island-wide provider of innovative wind energy solutions, was established in 2005 by a team of experienced engineers and wind energy experts. The company has around 8 branches located in different parts of the island, and for the purposes of this research, we have chosen the Kandy branch where there are approximately 65 employees. Out of those 65 employees, 50 were selected to participate in the survey. Over the past 6 years, Wind Vision has established itself as a leader in the wind energy industry, offering high-quality products and services that have earned the trust and loyalty of its customers. The company's head office, which manages all the important documents and information, is located in Kandy, Sri Lanka.

Prior to the pandemic, Wind Vision relied on a windows-based system to complete its daily tasks and operate its business. However, with the advent of remote work due to the pandemic, the company was forced to shift to a web-based system. This change allowed the company to continue communicating with its employees and clients, edit documents, hold meetings, and share data and information.

Despite the benefits of using these new technologies and software, Wind Vision is aware of the increased risk of cyber security threats that come with working remotely. The company's sensitive data and information are now exposed to the outside world, and this project aims to investigate the cyber security risks associated with remote work and provide recommendations for improving the company's security measures.

E Solutions - E Solutions by RNX, a leading provider of cutting-edge digital solutions, was founded in 1998 . The company operates through a network of 20 branches across the island, with the Negombo branch being selected for the research. There are 78 employees in the Negombo branch, out of which 50 were selected to participate in the survey. Over the past 10 years, E Solutions by RNX has established itself as a trusted and successful company, offering its customers the best in digital solutions and excellent customer service.

The head office of E Solutions by RNX, which manages all the company's records, is located in Negombo, Sri Lanka. Prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, the company relied on a windows-based system for its daily operations. However, with the rise of remote work due to the pandemic, the company was forced to switch to a web-based system. This required the use of new technologies and software, such as online collaboration tools and websites, to communicate, edit documents, conduct meetings, and share sensitive data and information.

While the new technologies have made remote work possible, they have also exposed the company to greater cyber security risks. This research project aims to investigate and analyze these risks, with the goal of developing recommendations to improve the company's cyber security measures and protect its sensitive data and information.

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1.2. Purpose of research

The research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" has two goals. First, it wants to find out what kind and how big of cybersecurity threats remote workers in Sri Lanka face. By finding out what kinds of threats remote workers face, the research will help raise awareness and teach remote workers about the dangers that cyber-criminals pose. This will let remote workers take the steps they need to keep themselves safe from these dangers.

The second goal of the research is to find out what steps remote workers are taking to protect themselves from these threats and how well they are working. By doing this, the research will find out what the best ways are for remote workers to protect themselves from cybersecurity threats. This information will help remote workers make smart decisions about their cybersecurity and take steps to protect their personal and work information. The results of this study will have a big effect on both organizations and remote workers. The research will help remote workers better understand the risks they face and take steps to protect themselves from these dangers. For businesses, the research will give them valuable information about the problems remote workers face and suggestions for how to improve their security. This will help protect and secure the personal and work information of people who work from home.

In conclusion, the research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" is very important in the digital age, where digital technologies are being used more and more to help people work from home. This research will help make sure that remote workers can work safely and securely and that organizations can protect their data and information. It will do this by giving valuable information about the problems remote workers face and making suggestions for how to improve their cybersecurity.

1.3. Significance of the Research

In today's rapidly changing digital world, research on "Cyber Security Threats to Remote Workers in Sri Lanka" is very important. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, more people are working from home, which increases the risk of cyber security threats. Research will tell us a lot about the problems faced by remote workers in Sri Lanka, and to clearly identify what leads to increasing in cyber-attacks and suggest ways to improve their security. This will help ensure that people working from home can do their jobs safely and securely, and businesses can keep their data and information safe. The results of this research will also add to the growing body of knowledge about the problems faced by remote workers and the actions that can be taken to solve these problems.

The research will inform policy makers, organizations and other key people about how important cyber security is for remote workers and what needs to be done to keep them safe. The research will also be used to develop cybersecurity education and training programs for remote workers. These programs will be critical to improving their cyber security and protecting their personal and work data.

In conclusion, the research on “Cyber Security Threats to Remote Workers in Sri Lanka” is a timely and important study that has far-reaching implications for remote workers and organizations in the country. The results of this research will help ensure that remote workers can work safely and securely, and that organizations can protect their data and information in the face of growing cyber security threats.

1.4 Research objectives

RO1: To identifying cybersecurity threats experienced by remote workers during the pandemic period.

RO2: To understand the challenges remote workers face in protecting their personal and work-related information and to identify solutions for Cyber Security threats.

RO3: To observe if the companies are providing their employees with the necessary training and education to protect against cyber-attacks while working remotely.

RO4: To assess how well current safeguards protect against cyberattacks.

1.5 Research Sub objectives

- Do a literature review to find out what you already know about the cyber security threats that remote workers face.
- To survey and talk to remote workers in Sri Lanka to find out about their experiences with cyber threats.
- To figure out if the security measures already in place, like anti-virus software, firewalls, and encryption, are enough to protect remote workers from cyber threats.
- To help organizations, policymakers, and individuals improve the security of remote workers and reduce the risks that come with working from home.

1.6 Research questions

1. How has the pandemic affected cyber security for remote workers in Sri Lanka?
2. Are remote workers in Sri Lanka receiving proper training and guidance from their companies on how to protect themselves from cybersecurity threats?
3. What measures are remote workers in Sri Lanka taking to protect themselves from cybersecurity threats, and how effective are these measures?
4. What can organizations, policymakers, and individuals do to enhance the cybersecurity of remote workers in Sri Lanka and minimize the risks associated with remote work?

1.7 Hypothesis

H₁ – Lack of knowledge about how to be safe from cyber-attacks are causing an increase in hacking.

H₀ – Lack of knowledge about how to be safe from cyber-attacks are not causing an increase in hacking.

1.8 Thesis structure

CHAPTER 1 - Introduction

Under the introduction, the topic that the research is going to be done on would be explained in a way that would help the reader understand the research that was done. In this section, we'll talk about what social media is, what digital well-being is, and how addicted a user is likely to be to a certain media site. Aside from that, the problem and the research's purpose would also be mentioned and explained using the research's goals. There would also be a list of the questions that need to be answered by the research.

CHAPTER 2 - Literature Review

This section would list all of the relevant literature to the research topic. Philosophy, representations, and research that have already been done would be used to explain social media addiction and how it affects digital health. In this chapter, the conceptual framework that was used will also be shown.

CHAPTER 3 - Methodology

This chapter will show all of the methods used in the study, such as the questionnaire, the model of the questions, and how the questionnaire was set up. Also, the research's population, data collection, validity, reliability, generalizability, and homoscedasticity will all be broken down and explained. After that, this chapter will talk about the ethical issues that come up because of the study.

CHAPTER 4 - Presentation of Results

This chapter shows the results of the analysis of the data from the 150 users from the target population who filled out the survey. The numbers from the results were looked at with the help of the analysis software SPSS and Excel. On the collected data, a Demographic Analysis, a Correlation Analysis, and a Regression Analysis were done, and the results and their analysis were given.

CHAPTER 5 - Conclusions and Recommendations

Each piece of analyzed data would be explained, and then recommendations that can be used in the research would be given. This chapter would also include a personal reflection on the project, its limitations, the benefits to the researcher, and the benefits to the organization.

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CHAPTER 2 - LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Literature Review

Because of the development of new technologies and the expansion of the freelance economy, working from home has become increasingly common in recent years. However, new cybersecurity threats have emerged as a result of this change because of the increased prevalence of remote access to sensitive data by employees. As remote work becomes more popular in Sri Lanka in the wake of the COVID-19 outbreak, it is crucial to have a thorough understanding of the cybersecurity risks encountered by remote workers and the best ways to protect against them. (redcentric, 2021)

There is a wealth of information available on the topic of cybersecurity threats to remote workers. This literature covers a wide range of topics, including the different types of cyber threats, the difficulties remote workers face in keeping their data secure, and the steps both businesses and individuals can take to improve their cybersecurity. The purpose of this chapter is to provide an overview of the present state of knowledge on cybersecurity threats to remote workers in Sri Lanka by reviewing the extant literature on these topics.

2.1.1 Different Cybersecurity threats

Cybersecurity concerns, such as phishing schemes, malware attacks, ransomware, and data breaches, are a real concern for remote employees. People fall victim to phishing schemes when they click on links in suspicious emails or visit malicious websites that ask for personal information such as passwords or banking information. Malware assaults, in which harmful software is installed on a computer, can cause data theft, unauthorized access to personal information, and the interruption of normal computer functions. Ransomware is malicious software that encrypts a user's files and then requests money in exchange for releasing the data. Theft of private information, such as names, addresses, and financial records, due to a data breach can have devastating effects on victims and their respective institutions.

Figure 1. Cyber threats | Source (Medium, 2021)

Cybersecurity threats are any actions or attacks that are done on purpose to make computer systems, networks, and data less safe. There are many different kinds of cybersecurity threats, and each one has its own traits and ways of attacking. In this section, we'll talk about some of the most common cyber threats that remote workers in Sri Lanka have to deal with. These are some of the most common cyber threats that people who work from home in Sri Lanka have to deal with. It's important for remote workers to be aware of these risks and take steps to protect themselves, like using strong passwords, staying away from public Wi-Fi networks, and being careful when opening email attachments or links. Also, companies should give their remote workers training and tools to help them recognize and deal with these threats.

- **Malware** is bad software, such as viruses, worms, Trojan horses, and ransomware. These kinds of threats can get on a computer and do damage by stealing sensitive information, changing system settings, or locking users out of their own devices. For instance, a virus could infect the computer of a remote worker and steal their login information. This would give the attacker access to sensitive information on the computer or in cloud-based services.
- **Phishing** is a type of social engineering attack that tries to trick people into giving out sensitive information, like their login credentials or credit card numbers. This type of threat usually comes in the form of an email or message that looks like it came from a trusted source, like a bank or online store, and asks the recipient to click a link or download an attachment. For example, a remote worker might get an email that looks like it came from the IT department of their company and asks them to enter their login information to use a new remote access system.
- **Man-in-the-middle (MITM)** attacks happen when an attacker listens in on a conversation between two parties by pretending to be a trusted party. For example, a remote worker may connect to a public Wi-Fi network and find that an attacker has taken over their connection and is watching everything they do online.
- **Denial-of-service (DoS)** attacks try to stop a website or online service from being used by flooding it with too much traffic. This kind of threat can do a lot of damage to a company's reputation and income, and it can also lead to sensitive information being leaked. For example, a DoS attack could make it so that a worker who works from home can't use their company's email or file-sharing service.

These are some of the most common cyber threats that people who work from home in Sri Lanka have to deal with. It's important for remote workers to be aware of these risks and take steps to protect themselves, like using strong passwords, staying away from public Wi-Fi networks, and being careful when opening email attachments or links. Also, companies should give their remote workers training and tools to help them recognize and deal with these threats.

2.1.2 Issues that need to be addressed by remote workers.

A lack of access to corporate security measures, insufficient personal cybersecurity practices, and a lack of understanding about cyber risks are just some of the obstacles that stand in the way of protecting personal and work-related information for remote workers. Data breaches and cyber-attacks can be made more likely if remote workers use their own devices, like laptops or cellphones, to access company data. Public Wi-Fi, for example, can put telecommuters at risk because it is an insecure network.

There are a few things that remote workers need to do to make sure that their devices, networks, and data are safe:

- **Lack of security training:** Many companies may not give their remote workers the right security training, leaving them open to cyber-attacks. It's important for people who work from home to know what risks come with the job and get training on how to protect themselves.
- **Unsecured home networks:** Many remote workers may be using unsecure home networks, which can leave their devices and data open to attack. Remote workers should make sure their home networks are secure and protect their systems with firewalls and other security measures.
- **Use of personal devices:** Many remote workers may use their own laptops, smartphones, and tablets to access sensitive information and do work-related tasks. It's important for remote workers to know the risks that come with using their own devices and to take steps to protect their data.
- **Public Wi-Fi:** Remote workers may use public Wi-Fi networks, which can be vulnerable to man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks and other security threats. When accessing sensitive information, people who work from home shouldn't use public Wi-Fi networks. Instead, they should use virtual private networks (VPNs) or other security measures.

- **Phishing attacks:** Remote workers often have to deal with phishing attacks, which can lead to sensitive information being stolen and devices and networks being hacked. When opening emails and links, remote workers should be careful, and they shouldn't give sensitive information to people they don't know or trust.
- **Poor password management:** Many remote workers use weak passwords or reuse passwords, which leaves their accounts open to attack. Remote workers should use strong, unique passwords to protect their accounts. They should also use two-factor authentication (2FA) or other security measures.

By taking care of these problems, remote workers can lower the risk of cyber-attacks and protect their devices, networks, and data. Also, companies should give their remote workers the tools and support they need to deal with these problems and keep their systems secure.

2.1.3 Precautions to strengthen online safety.

There are numerous steps that businesses and individuals may take to improve remote employees' cyber security. Taking precautions against cybercrime can require both technological solutions that remote workers can take to improve cybersecurity.

Remote workers can improve their online safety by taking the following steps:

- **Security training:** Remote workers who get security training regularly can learn about the risks of working from home and how to protect themselves from cyber-attacks.
- **Strong passwords:** People who work from home should use strong passwords that are unique to them and change them often. Two-factor authentication (2FA) or multi-factor authentication (MFA) can give you more security.
- **Using sing VPNs:** Virtual private networks (VPNs) can protect remote workers from man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks and other security threats by encrypting the data that is sent over the internet.
- **Firewall and anti-virus software:** Remote workers should install firewall and anti-virus software on their devices and keep it up-to-date to protect them from cyber-attacks.
- **Secure home networks:** Remote workers should protect their devices and data by securing their home networks with strong passwords and encryption.

- Public Wi-Fi should not be used for sensitive tasks, and remote workers should use VPNs or other security measures to access sensitive information when they need to.
- Phishing attacks should be known to remote workers, and they shouldn't open emails or click on links from sources they don't trust.
- **Regular software updates:** People who work from home should update their operating systems and software on a regular basis to protect themselves from known security flaws.
- **Data backup:** Regular data backups can protect remote workers from losing data and let them get their data back if their systems are hacked.

By taking these steps, remote workers can improve their online safety and lower their chances of being attacked. Organizations should also give remote workers the tools and support they need to put these measures into action and keep their systems secure. The literature study concludes by emphasizing the significance of knowing the cybersecurity risks faced by remote employees in Sri Lanka and the ways in which to mitigate them. Organizations, policymakers, and people can all benefit from this study's findings as they fight to reduce the dangers of remote employment.

2.1 Conceptual framework

A conceptual framework is a picture of the most important ideas and how they relate to each other in a research study. It gives you a way to organize and understand the different parts of your research. It also helps you make sure that your study is well-designed and makes sense.

In the context of a study on cybersecurity threats to remote workers in Sri Lanka, a conceptual framework can help to:

- Identify the most important ideas and variables in the study, such as the types of cybersecurity threats, the level of security training given to remote workers, and the effect of the pandemic on remote work.
- Find out how the different ideas and variables are related to each other and highlight any possible cause-and-effect relationships.
- Give a visual representation of the study's hypotheses and research questions. This will help make sure the study is focused and well-structured.

- Help with gathering and analyzing data, making sure that the data fits with the study's hypotheses and research questions.
- Help get the results of the study across in a clear and consistent way so that other people can easily understand and interpret them.

In conclusion, a conceptual framework is a useful tool for any research study, but it is especially important for a study about cybersecurity threats to remote workers in Sri Lanka. It can help make sure that the study is well-planned, follows a logical path, and communicates its results clearly.

Figure 2. Conceptual framework | Source (Author's work)

CHAPTER 3 - METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research philosophy

3.1.1 Research onion

The research onion is a visual model that shows the different steps of a research study, from defining the research problem to presenting the results.

Figure 3. Research onion | Source (15 writers, 2017)

Each of the six layers of the research onion represents a different step in the research process:

- **Philosophy:** This layer is where the study's guiding philosophy is written down. This could include, among other things, positivism, realism, or interpretivism.
- **Approach:** This layer shows how the research was done in general. It could be qualitative, quantitative, or a mix of both.
- **Strategy:** This layer shows what kind of research will be done, like a survey, a case study, or an experiment.
- **Choices:** This layer shows the methods and techniques that will be used to collect and analyze the data, like interviews, questionnaires, or statistical analysis.

- **Time horizon:** This layer shows the time frame for the research study, such as how long the study will last and when data will be collected.
- **Techniques and procedures:** This layer shows the setting in which the research is done, including the people who are being studied and where the research is being done.

3.1.2 Positivism Research philosophy, reason to choose it.

Positivism is a way of doing research that focuses on using scientific and real-world methods to study social and behavioral phenomena. It is based on the idea that social and behavioral phenomena can be measured and analyzed in an objective way, and that the results of these measurements and analyses can be used to make theories and generalizations about the world. , (Dudovskiy, 2009)

positivism can be used to support the following aspects of the research:

- **Objectivity:** Positivism is based on the idea that reality is objective, which means that it exists regardless of how different people see it. In this study, positivism would be used to help measure cybersecurity threats, security training, and how the pandemic affected remote work in a fair way.
- **Empiricism:** Positivism stresses the importance of empirical evidence, which is evidence based on observation and experience. In this study, positivism would be used to help collect real-world information about how cyber threats affect remote workers in Sri Lanka and what they do to protect themselves.
- **Generalizability:** Positivism is based on the idea that the results of a study can be applied to other populations that are similar to the one studied. In this study, positivism would be used to show that the results could be applied to other remote workers in Sri Lanka and to other remote workers in countries that are similar to Sri Lanka.
- **Scientific method:** Positivism agrees that the scientific method is a good way to find out about reality. In this study, positivism would be used to support the systematic and rigorous way of collecting and analyzing data, which is a key part of the scientific method.

Positivism was chosen as the research philosophy for the "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" study because it fits well with the goal of the study, which was to understand and measure the nature and extent of the cybersecurity threats remote workers in Sri Lanka face. The positivist approach stresses the use of objective and empirical methods,

like surveys and statistical analysis, to collect and analyze data on cybersecurity threats. This method works well for a research study that wants to find out how common and bad cybersecurity threats are to remote workers.

Also, the positivist approach stresses the importance of being objective and doing research in a way that is planned and controlled. This is important for a study on cybersecurity threats because it helps make sure that the results are reliable and can be used in other situations. It also makes sure that the results are not skewed by personal biases or different ways of looking at the data.

In conclusion, positivism was chosen as the research philosophy for the study on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" because it fits with the research goal and focuses on objective, empirical, and systematic methods, which are good for a study of this kind.

3.2 Research approach

The research approach is the overall plan and strategy for how a research study will be done. In the context of the research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka," the research method was reductive. (Verywell Mind, n.d.)

The reductive approach, which is also called reductionism, is a way to do research that tries to simplify and understand complex things by breaking them down into smaller, easier-to-understand parts. In this research, the reductive method was used to look at the cybersecurity risks that Sri Lankan workers who work from home face.

INTERIOR OF VAUCANSON'S AUTOMATIC DUCK.

A, clockwork; *B*, pump; *C*, mill for grinding grain; *E*, intestinal tube;
J, bill; *H*, head; *M*, feet.

Figure 4. Reductionism| Source (Wikipedia)

The goal of the study was to get a clear picture of the nature and scope of these threats by breaking down the complex and multifaceted topic of cybersecurity into its individual parts.

The reductive method is often used in quantitative research. It involves gathering data with standard tools, like surveys or questionnaires, google form (a survey is used in this research). Then, based on the results of this analysis, conclusions are made about the thing being studied.

In conclusion, the reductive approach was chosen for this research because it offered a systematic and structured way to study the complex phenomenon of cybersecurity threats to remote workers in Sri Lanka. The method let a lot of data be collected, and statistical methods were used to find patterns and relationships. This gave a quantitative and empirical understanding of the phenomenon.

Quantitative and qualitative, Inductive and deductive research methods

There are two main ways to do research: quantitative research methods and qualitative research methods. Quantitative research methods focus on collecting and analyzing numerical data to answer research questions and test hypotheses. They are often used in positivist research and are used to describe, explain, and make predictions about phenomena. Surveys, experiments, and statistical analysis are all examples of quantitative research methods.

On the other hand, qualitative research methods focus on gathering and analyzing non-numerical data, like words, images, and observations. They are often part of an interpretive or constructivist approach to research, and they are used to learn more about things like experiences, perspectives, and meanings. In-depth interviews, focus groups, and ethnography are all types of qualitative research methods.

Researchers use inductive and deductive research methods to come up with and test hypotheses.

With inductive research methods, observations are used to come up with hypotheses, which are then tested. Inductive research is often used in conjunction with qualitative research methods, and it is used to learn more about complicated things in depth. Deductive research methods start with a set of known theories or hypotheses and use them to guide how data is collected and analyzed. Deductive research is often used with quantitative research methods to test hypotheses and make predictions about things.

In conclusion, there are two main ways to do research: quantitative research methods and qualitative research methods. Inductive and deductive research methods describe how hypotheses are made and tested. Both approaches and methods have pros and cons, and the choice of method will depend on the research question, the research goals, and the nature of the phenomenon being studied.

Quantitative and inductive research methods was used

The research on "Cybersecurity threats to people in Sri Lanka who work from home" used both quantitative and inductive research methods.

Quantitative research is a type of research that is based on gathering and analyzing numbers. In this study, quantitative methods were used to collect and analyze information about how many and what kinds of cybersecurity threats remote workers in Sri Lanka face. This was done by asking a large number of participants to fill out surveys or questionnaires that were the same for everyone. (Kahlke, Sherbino and Monteiro, 2022)

On the other hand, inductive research is a type of research in which theory is built from real-world observations. Based on the results of the quantitative data analysis, the inductive method was used in this study to come up with theories about the cybersecurity threats that remote workers in Sri Lanka face. The results were used to find patterns and relationships between the variables, which were then used to come up with hypotheses and theories about the thing being studied.

In conclusion, the research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" used both quantitative and inductive research methods. The quantitative methods were used to collect and analyze data, while the inductive methods were used to come up with theories based on the results of the data analysis.

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3.3 Research strategy

A survey-based research methodology was used as the research technique for the study titled "Cybersecurity threats to those who are working remotely in Sri Lanka." the study was conducted in Sri Lanka. The research design of a survey was selected because it enabled the collecting of data from a large number of participants in a methodical and standardized fashion. This was the primary reason for the selection of the survey research design. Because of this, a thorough picture of the scale and nature of the cybersecurity dangers that remote employees in Sri Lanka confront was presented.

The following is a rundown of the primary stages involved in the research strategy based on surveys:

- **Sampling** was the initial phase, and it required determining the sample size and selecting a sample of distant workers in Sri Lanka that was representative of the entire population. This was accomplished through the use of a selection method known as convenience sampling, in which participants were chosen on the basis of their willingness and availability to take part in the research.
- **The collection of data** consisted of using standardized questionnaires in order to amass the necessary information. The purpose of the survey was to collect information about the participants' prior encounters with cybersecurity risks, the sorts of risks they had been exposed to, as well as their level of knowledge and awareness regarding preventative cybersecurity measures.
- **Analyzing the Data:** The information obtained through the survey was analyzed by employing statistical approaches, such as descriptive statistics, in order to establish patterns and determine the nature of the correlations between the different variables.

The findings of the data analysis were then used to provide an interpretation of the type and magnitude of the cybersecurity dangers that are confronted by remote employees in Sri Lanka. Last but not least, the findings were put to use in the process of drawing conclusions regarding the issue that was under investigation and developing suggestions for enhancing cybersecurity protections for remote employees in Sri Lanka.

In conclusion, the study technique that was based on surveys provided a methodical and structured approach to the collection and analysis of data on the cybersecurity risks that remote workers in Sri Lanka confront. The development of a full understanding of the phenomenon

that was being examined was made possible by the application of standardized questionnaires and methods of statistical analysis.

Why survey based.

The "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" study used a survey-based research design for several reasons:

- **Representativeness:** Surveys make it possible to get information from a large number of people who are a good representation of the population being studied. In the context of this research, this meant that a representative sample of remote workers in Sri Lanka could be chosen, and data could be collected from them to get a full picture of the number and types of cybersecurity threats they face.
- **Standardization:** Surveys make it possible to use standardized tools, like questionnaires, to gather information. This standardization helps to make sure that data is collected in a consistent and organized way. It also makes it less likely that data collection will be biased or full of mistakes.
- **Ease of Collecting Data:** Surveys can be given in many different ways, such as online, by mail, or over the phone. This makes it easy to get information from people in different parts of the world, such as remote workers.
- **Cost-effective:** Surveys are less expensive than other types of research, like experiments or case studies, so they are a good choice for this research.
- **Flexibility:** Surveys can be made to collect a wide range of data, both quantitative and qualitative. This makes them a good choice for research that needs to be flexible.

In conclusion, the survey-based research design was chosen for the research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" because it was representative, standardized, easy to collect data for, cost-effective, and flexible. Using surveys made it possible to get information from a large and representative sample of remote workers in Sri Lanka. This gave a full picture of the number and types of cybersecurity threats they face.

3.4 Research Choice

For the study on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work from home in Sri Lanka," a survey-based quantitative research method was chosen. The reason for this choice was to get numbers about how remote workers think and feel about cybersecurity threats and what their companies are doing to deal with these threats. The survey made it possible to get information from a large number of remote workers, which gave a broad and accurate picture of what was being studied (Cramer, 2005).

Figure 5. Methodological choice | Source (open.library.okstate.edu, 2019)

Mono-method research is a type of research design in which only one method is used to gather data and come up with results. Most of the time, this method is used when the research goal is clear and requires collecting numbers that can be analyzed quantitatively. On the other hand, mixed methods research is a type of research design in which both qualitative and quantitative research methods are used to collect and analyze data. This method is usually used when the research goal is complicated and needs both numbers and other kinds of data that can be analyzed in both qualitative and quantitative ways. (www.ipl.org,)

A single method was used for the research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka." The reason for this was that the research goal was clear: to get numbers about how remote workers see and deal with cybersecurity threats. The best way to get this information was through a survey-based plan.

We didn't use a mixed-methods approach because our research goal didn't need us to collect both numbers and other kinds of information. The goal of the research could be met by using a quantitative research method, like a survey-based design, which would give accurate and reliable information about how remote workers deal with cybersecurity threats.

3.5 Time frame

The research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work from home in Sri Lanka" was done between the dates of December 8, 2022 and January 15, 2023. Within this time frame, the research was done well, and the researchers were able to collect and analyze the data they needed to meet the research goal.

A set time frame is an important part of research design because it helps make sure the research is done quickly and well. A time frame helps to focus the research, make sure resources are used well, and make sure the research is done in a reasonable amount of time. In this study, I was able to focus on gathering and analyzing the data because they had a set amount of time to do so. This helped make sure that the research was done quickly and well, and that the results of the research were available on time.

Figure 6. Gantt chart | Source (Author's work)

3.6 Data collection procedures

Quantitative methods, like a survey, were used to gather information for the "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" study. The survey was done with the help of a Google Form that was sent to 150 people who worked at Wind Vision, E Solutions by RNX, and Western Papers. Out of the 150 forms that were sent, 108 were filled out and sent back, which was very helpful for the research.

The survey design was chosen as the way to gather information for this study because it made it possible to get a lot of information from a lot of people in a short amount of time. Using a

Google Form also made it possible to do the survey quickly and well, for a low cost and with little work on the back end.

The survey data was analyzed so that the research goals could be met and the research questions could be answered. Statistical methods like frequency analysis and cross-tabulation were used to look for patterns and trends in the data. This gave me useful information about the cybersecurity risks that people who work remotely in Sri Lanka face and the steps they take to protect themselves from these risks.

3.6.1 Type of Data

The type of data that was collected for the "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" study was quantitative. Quantitative data is information that can be measured and has numbers, like answers to survey questions. The survey asked people about the cybersecurity risks they face when working from home, how they felt about the training and support they got from their companies, and what they did to protect themselves from these risks. The answers to these questions made up the data that was collected.

Statistical analysis can be used to find patterns and trends in quantitative data, as well as to test hypotheses. In this study, statistical methods like frequency analysis and cross-tabulation were used to look at the survey data in order to find patterns and trends and learn more about the cybersecurity threats that remote workers in Sri Lanka face.

Overall, the use of quantitative data in this research gave valuable insights into the cybersecurity threats remote workers in Sri Lanka face and the steps they take to protect themselves from these threats. This helped to better understand the problems these people face and guided efforts to improve cybersecurity for remote workers in Sri Lanka.

3.6.2 Data Collection Method

The research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka" used a quantitative survey done with Google Forms to gather information. The goal of the survey was to find out what cybersecurity threats people who work from home face, how they feel about the training and support they get from their companies, and what steps they take to protect themselves from these threats.

The survey was sent to 150 people who worked from home in Sri Lanka for three different companies: Wind Vision, E Solutions by RNX, and Western Papers. Out of the 150 employees, 108 filled out the survey. This gave us important information about the cybersecurity risks

remote workers in Sri Lanka face. Using Google Forms as a tool for collecting data made it easy to send out and collect the survey electronically, which cut down on the time and resources needed to collect and analyze the data. Using a survey also made it possible to get standard data from a large number of people, which is helpful for statistical analysis and finding patterns and trends in the data.

Overall, the way the data for this study was collected gave us important information about the cybersecurity risks that remote workers in Sri Lanka face and the steps they take to protect themselves from these risks. This information will help us better understand the problems these people face and help us figure out how to make remote workers in Sri Lanka safer online.

3.6.3 Data Collection and Analyze Tools

In the study "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka," data was collected with Google Forms and analyzed with Excel and IBM SPSS. Google Forms was the main tool for collecting data because it made it easy and inexpensive to send the survey to a large number of people and get their answers electronically. The information gathered through Google Forms was then sent to Excel, where it was cleaned up and put in order so it could be analyzed. (TrustRadius, n.d.)

IBM SPSS was used to look at the data statistically, which made it possible to find patterns and trends in the answers. To sum up and make sense of the data, statistical methods like frequency analysis, cross-tabulation, and descriptive statistics were used. Regression analysis was also used to find out how the variables were related and test hypotheses.

With the help of Excel and IBM SPSS, the data from the survey could be analyzed quickly and thoroughly. The analysis's results gave important information about the cybersecurity risks that remote workers in Sri Lanka face and the steps they take to protect themselves from these risks.

Overall, using Google Forms, Excel, and IBM SPSS made it possible to collect and analyze data in a strong and reliable way. This gave us important information that will help us improve cybersecurity for remote workers in Sri Lanka.

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3.6.4 Questionnaire structure

Variable	Indicators	Measurement	Mean	STD. Deviation	Median
IVE1_AV	IV1_E1	Questioner	4.48	0.572	4.00
	IV1_E2	(Likert scale)	4.47	0.571	4.00
	IV1_E3		4.47	0.587	4.00
IVE2_AV	IV2_1	Questioner	4.45	0.570	4.00
	IV2_2	(Likert scale)	4.47	0.571	4.00
	IV2_3		4.51	0.604	5.00
IVE3_AV	IV3_1	Questioner	4.44	0.569	5.00
	IV3_2	(Likert scale)	4.49	0.588	4.00
	IV3_3		4.58	0.566	5.00
DV	DV1	Questioner	4.64	0.587	4.00
	DV2	(Likert scale)	4.38	0.559	4.00
	DV3		4.63	0.573	5.00

Table 1. Questionnaire structure | Source (Author's Work)

3.6.7 Data Storage

In order to safeguard the information that was gathered through the survey, we saved it in a number of different places. Both the forms and the responses were saved in separate locations; the first was on Google Drive, and the second was on the researcher's own computer. In order to maintain the reliability of the data, the outcomes of the analyses carried out with IBM SPSS were additionally kept and encrypted.

The possibility of information becoming corrupted or lost was lessened because several backups were kept. The legitimacy and validity of the research findings are directly impacted by the level of security afforded to the data storage.

3.7 Target population and sampling

This study looked at Western Papers Industries (Pvt) Ltd, Wind Vision Industries (Pvt) Ltd, and E Solutions by RNX. Each organization was chosen because it relies on technology and communication to work and function remotely during the pandemic. The survey asked 50 people from each company's chosen branch, for a total of 150 people. These people were chosen because they have dealt with pandemics and use technology, making them good sources for this study project on cyber security issues in remote work.

Morgan's table helps researchers determine sample size. The table assumes that a bigger sample size yields more accurate results but is more expensive and complex to administer. Morgan's chart helps researchers choose a sample size based on population size and precision. This optimizes sample size and precision. (KENPRO, 2012)

<i>Table for Determining Sample Size of a Known Population</i>									
N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S
10	10	100	80	280	162	800	260	2800	338
15	14	110	86	290	165	850	265	3000	341
20	19	120	92	300	169	900	269	3500	346
25	24	130	97	320	175	950	274	4000	351
30	28	140	103	340	181	1000	278	4500	354
35	32	150	108	360	186	1100	285	5000	357
40	36	160	113	380	191	1200	291	6000	361
45	40	170	118	400	196	1300	297	7000	364
50	44	180	123	420	201	1400	302	8000	367
55	48	190	127	440	205	1500	306	9000	368
60	52	200	132	460	210	1600	310	10000	370
65	56	210	136	480	214	1700	313	15000	375
70	59	220	140	500	217	1800	317	20000	377
75	63	230	144	550	226	1900	320	30000	379
80	66	240	148	600	234	2000	322	40000	380
85	70	250	152	650	242	2200	327	50000	381
90	73	260	155	700	248	2400	331	75000	382
95	76	270	159	750	254	2600	335	1000000	384

Note: N is Population Size; S is Sample Size *Source: Krejcie & Morgan, 1970*

Table 2. Morgans table | Source (qhaireenizzati.wordpress.com, 2016)

Researchers must know the population's size and accuracy before using Morgan's table. The table indicates the minimum sample size based on these two factors. This sample size is suitable for accurate results if it is randomly picked and representative of the population.

Morgan's table is especially useful in investigations where sample size greatly affects validity and reliability. Sri Lankan remote workers from Wind Vision, E Solutions by RNX, and Western Papers were chosen to take part in the study because they were part of the population of interest for the investigation. After using Morgan's table to figure it out, the number of people in the sample was found to be 108. The questionnaire was given to all 150 employees, but only 108 were able to fill it out and send it back. This makes the total number of respondents 108. 150 people from each company were chosen, and after looking at the Morgans table, the sample size will be 108.

Using a sample made it easier and less expensive to collect data, but it still led to important conclusions that could be applied to the whole population. To make sure that the research results are a true reflection of the experiences and thoughts of remote workers in Sri Lanka about cybersecurity issues, the sample was chosen to be representative of the population being studied.

Simple Random Sampling was the sampling method used for the "Cybersecurity Threats to People Working Remotely in Sri Lanka" research project. This method was chosen because there was no other way to do the study with the data that was available. Simple random sampling is a way to pick a sample from a larger population that is easy and fair. The sample is chosen at random from the whole population, so everyone has an equal chance of being in it. This method was chosen for the research project because it made sure the sample was a good representation of the whole population and made it easy to apply the results to the whole population.

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3.8 The selection of participants

We chose the people who would take part in the study using a method called sampling. Sampling involves choosing a small part of a larger population to learn about the population as a whole. The target population for this study is the people who work at Wind Vision, E Solutions by RNX, and Western Papers. These people were chosen to take part in the study.

Company name?

107 responses

Figure 7. Participants of each company | Source (Author's data)

The goal of sampling was to reduce the time and money needed to get information from the whole population, which was the focus of the study. Morgan's table was used to come up with a sample size of 108, and 150 employees were given a questionnaire. Only 108 of those employees filled out the survey, so the sample size was complete. Out of the 108 people who took part, 33 came from Wind Vision, 36 came from E Solutions by RNX, and 39 came from Western Papers.

3.9 Reliability, Validity, and Generalizability

3.9.1 Reliability

When it comes to research, reliability means how consistent and stable the results of the study are. In other words, it checks how consistent the results are over time, making sure that the same results would be found if the study were done again in the same way. In the context of

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items

Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha | Source (Author's data)

the research you did on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka," you could improve the reliability by using standard methods and tools for collecting data, as well as a large sample size and a sample that is representative of the target population. Using a well-known survey tool and making sure the data are consistent within themselves can also make the results more trustworthy. (Tyler Olhorst, 2019).

At the end of the day, the goal is to make sure that the results of the research are reliable and can be used by other researchers. Also, the size of the sample, how well it represents the whole, and the quality of the data collected can all affect how reliable the research is. To make sure the research is accurate, it's important to follow strict research methods, use the right measures and data collection methods, and make sure the data is analyzed in a fair and accurate way.

3.9.2 Validity

Validity is a term for how true and accurate the research results are. It's important because it makes sure that the research results show what's really going on with the people being studied. In this study, the validity of the results was kept by making sure that the survey questions were related to the research topic and that the people who took the survey were representative of the target population. The people who took the survey were also given clear instructions on how to do it, which cut down on the chance of mistakes or misunderstandings. Statistical methods were used to look at the data, which helped to reduce the effect of any biases or confounding variables. (Anon., n.d.)

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Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component	
	1	2
DV1	.795	
DV3	.753	
IV1_E2	.733	
IV2_1	.645	
IV2_3	.592	.403
IV3_2	.574	
IV1_E3		.721
DV2		.718
IV2_2		.662
IV1_E1		.630
IV3_3		.577
IV3_1		.530

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Table 4. Rotated Component Matrix | Source (Author's data)

By making sure that the results are correct, this research gives accurate and reliable information about the cybersecurity risks that people who work remotely in Sri Lanka face.

3.9.2 Generalizability

Generalizability is how well the results of a study can be used in other places and with other people. In other words, it means being able to use the research results outside of the sample and the situation in which the study was done. Generalizability is an important thing to think about when doing research on the topic "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka." This is because the sample of employees from three companies (Wind Vision, E solutions by RNX, and Western Papers) may not represent the experiences and attitudes of remote workers in other companies or industries.

To make sure that the results can be applied to the whole population, the sample should be a good representation of it, and the research design should be carefully planned and carried out. In this case, a purposeful sampling method was used to choose the sample, and Morgan's table was used to figure out the sample size to make sure it was representative. Also, efforts were made to reduce biases and keep track of other factors that could change the results.

Generalizability is important because it helps researchers apply their findings to other groups. This can have a big effect on cybersecurity policy, practice, and decision-making. Because of this, it is important to make sure that the research results can be used by other remote workers in Sri Lanka and beyond.

3.10 Ethical issues of the research study

Ethics are a very important part of any research study. It is important to make sure that the participants' rights are protected and that the research is done in a fair, accurate, and safe way. For the study "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka," it's important to think about a number of ethical issues to make sure the results are valid and reliable.

Before the research can start, the participants must first give their informed consent. This includes giving a clear explanation of why the research is being done, how the data will be collected, and what the risks and benefits of taking part might be.

Second, the participants' privacy and right to remain anonymous must be protected. This means that the information gathered shouldn't reveal who the participant is, and it should be kept safe and secret.

Third, it's important to keep the participants from getting hurt, both physically and emotionally. This means avoiding sensitive topics that might upset the participant and making sure that the data collected won't hurt them in any way.

Lastly, the results of the study should be used to help society, not to make money for yourself. This means that the results should be reported correctly, without being changed or made up, and shouldn't be used for any commercial or unethical purposes.

In conclusion, ethical issues must be carefully thought about and dealt with at every step of the research process to make sure the study is done in a fair and responsible way.

CHAPTER 4 - PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

4.1 Demographic Analysis

Demographic analysis is the process of collecting, sorting, and analyzing information about the people who took part in the research. In the context of the research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka," demographic analysis helps to understand the socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of the sample population. Some of the things that could be looked at in this study are age, gender, level of education, job, income, and number of years on the job.

Most of the time, self-reported questionnaires are used to get this kind of information, which can help describe the background and traits of the participants. Demographic analysis can be used to find out if the sample population is representative of the target population and if the results of the research can be applied to other populations with similar characteristics.

It is important to do a demographic analysis because it tells you important things about the people who are taking part and can help you figure out if the results of the study are affected by any particular demographic group. The results of the demographic analysis can also be used to find any possible confounding variables that could change the results of the research.

Comparative Studies

Company name?

107 responses

Figure 8. Comparative Study of company | Source (Author's data)

Out of 107 employees who completed the questionnaire, 33 (30.8%) were from Wind Vision, 36 (33.6%) from E Solutions by RNX, and 39 (36.4%) from Western Papers. These results demonstrate the three target firms' varied workforce.

Age

102 responses

Figure 9. Comparative Study of age | Source (Author's data)

The question has 102 respondents, with the majority aged 30–36. High-age participation were scarce. This shows that a substantial component of the target population for this research is between 30 and 36 years old and that the higher and lower age groups have fewer participants.

Educational level

108 responses

Figure 10. Comparative Study of education | Source (Author's data)

70.4% of 108 respondents have degrees, while 29.6% have diplomas. This suggests that most Wind vision, E solutions by RNX, and Western papers employees are college graduates. The data indicates the importance of education in the employment sector and employers' efforts to hire higher-educated workers. This data can show how company employees' education levels affect their performance and contributions.

Salary

108 responses

Figure 11. Comparative Study of salary | Source (Author's data)

27 employees (25%) reported salaries above 250000 LKR. 52 (48.11%) workers make 175000–250000 LKR. The smallest group, 8 (7.4%), reported a salary between 75000 and 125000 LKR, while 21 (19.4%) reported a salary between 125000 and 175000. These findings show the pay distribution at Wind Vision, E Solutions by RNX, and Western Papers.

Hometown?

108 responses

Figure 12. Comparative Study of hometown | Source (Author's data)

The bulk of 108 respondents are Westerners. The target companies, Wind Vision, E Solutions by RNX, and Western Papers, have the most Western-based employees. This information helps comprehend Sri Lanka's remote workforce demographics and cybersecurity threats. This data may reveal remote workers' regional vulnerabilities and enable targeted cybersecurity measures.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Correlation Analysis is a statistical method used to look at how two or more variables in a study are related to each other. In the research on "Cybersecurity threats to people who work remotely in Sri Lanka," the data from the survey forms that employee of Wind vision, E solutions by RNX, and Western papers filled out can be analyzed with statistical tools like IBM SPSS to find the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, which shows the strength and direction of the relationship between the variables. By doing the correlation analysis, the researchers can learn more about the factors that might affect how serious people think cybersecurity threats are. They can then make suggestions to improve security measures for remote workers in Sri Lanka.

Correlation analysis is a statistical method that looks at how two or more variables are related to each other. The correlation coefficient is a way to figure out how strong and in what direction two variables are linked. When one variable goes up, the other variable also goes up, and vice versa. With a negative correlation, when one variable goes up, the other one goes down, and vice versa. The correlation coefficient can have a value between -1 and 1. A value of -1 means that there is a perfect negative correlation, 0 means that there is no correlation, and a value of 1 means that there is a perfect positive correlation.

Figure 13. correlation coefficient| Source (Cuemath, 2020)

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
.90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00)	Very high positive (negative) correlation
.70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90)	High positive (negative) correlation
.50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70)	Moderate positive (negative) correlation
.30 to .50 (-.30 to -.50)	Low positive (negative) correlation
.00 to .30 (.00 to -.30)	negligible correlation

Figure 14. correlation values | Source (Cuemath, 2020)

Correlation analysis is important because it can help find relationships between different variables that can be used to make predictions or help make decisions. For example, in a research study, if there is a positive relationship between age and salary, it could mean that people's salaries tend to go up as they get older. Organizations can use this information to decide on things like promotions, pay, and other HR policies. Correlation analysis can also be used to find variables that confuse or change the relationship between two other variables. This can be important for figuring out how the relationship works in the first place.

Correlations

		DV	IVE1_AV	IVE2_AV	IVE3_AV
DV	Pearson Correlation	1	.734**	.704**	.769**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	108	108	108	108
IVE1_AV	Pearson Correlation	.734**	1	.583**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	
	N	108	108	108	108
IVE2_AV	Pearson Correlation	.704**	.583**	1	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		
	N	108	108	108	108
IVE3_AV	Pearson Correlation	.769**	.769**	1	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	108	108	108	108

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 5. Correlation values | Source (Author's data)

4.2.1 RO2

Figure 15. Frequency Chart | Source (Author's data)

4.2.2 RO3

Figure 16. Frequency Chart | Source (Author's data)

4.2.3 RO4

Figure 17. Frequency Chart | Source (Author's data)

4.3 Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a way to use statistics to figure out how a dependent variable and one or more independent variables affect each other. The goal of regression analysis is to figure out what happens to the dependent variable when the independent variables change. It's important to realize that the fact that the dependent and independent variables are related does not mean that one caused the other. The regression equation is a mathematical way to show how the dependent variable and the independent variables relate to each other. It shows the values of the regression analysis. (Gallo, 2015)

The diagram shows the regression equation $Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \epsilon_i$. Labels with arrows point to each term: 'Dependent Variable' points to Y_i , 'Population Y intercept' points to β_0 , 'Population Slope Coefficient' points to β_1 , 'Independent Variable' points to X_i , and 'Random Error term' points to ϵ_i . A blue bracket under $\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i$ is labeled 'Linear component', and another blue bracket under ϵ_i is labeled 'Random Error component'.

Figure 18. Regression Analysis formula | Source (sixsigmadsi.com)

The regression equation is usually written as $Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_nX_n$, where Y is the dependent variable, $X_1, X_2, \dots,$ and X_n are independent variables, and $b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots,$ and b_n are regression coefficients that show the strength and direction of the relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable. The size of the regression coefficients ranges from -1 to 1, with a value closer to 1 indicating a strong positive relationship, a value closer to -1 indicating a strong negative relationship, and a value closer to 0 indicating a weak relationship.

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4.3.1 RO1

Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: DV1

Equation	R Square	Model Summary				Sig.	Parameter Estimates	
		F	df1	df2	Constant		b1	
Linear	.182	23.646	1	106	<.001	1.779	.639	

The independent variable is IVE1_AV.

Table 6. Regression Analysis | Source (Author's data)

Figure 19. Regression Analysis Chart | Source (Author's data)

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4.3.2 RO2

Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: DV1

Equation	R Square	Model Summary				Parameter Estimates	
		F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	.261	37.517	1	106	<.001	1.550	.690

The independent variable is IVE2_AV.

Table 7. . Regression Analysis | Source (Author's data)

Figure 20. Regression Analysis Chart | Source (Author's data)

4.3.3 RO3

Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: DV1

Equation	R Square	Model Summary				Sig.	Parameter Estimates	
		F	df1	df2	Constant		b1	
Linear	.276	40.409	1	106	<.001	1.377	.724	

The independent variable is IVE3_AV.

Table 8. Regression Analysis | Source (Author's data)

Figure 21. Regression Analysis Chart | Source (Author's data)

CHAPTER 5 - CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Conclusions summarize findings and their implications. The researcher presents their findings and interpretations in this final step. The conclusion summarizes the findings and concludes the study. It describes the research issue and proposes solutions or next steps based on the findings. The conclusion proves the research's validity and reliability. It informs and guides future research on the topic. The conclusion summarizes the research and its implications.

5.1.1 RO1

Correlation: In this study, the amount of hacking was the thing that was being studied, and lack of education and knowledge was the thing that was being studied. The correlation coefficient between the two variables was found to be 0.734, which shows that they are strongly linked. This means that as the number of people who don't have enough education and knowledge grows, the number of people who hack also grows. This shows that a lack of knowledge is a big reason why the number of hackers among remote workers in Sri Lanka is going up. By understanding this relationship, organizations can take the steps they need to educate their employees and reduce the risk of hacking and other cyber security threats. So, correlation analysis helps us figure out how variables are related and can give us important information about the problem we're trying to solve.

Regression: In this study, "hacking is getting worse" is the dependent variable, and "lack of education and proper knowledge" is the independent variable. With a coefficient value of 0.734, the regression analysis shows that there is a strong link between not having enough education and knowledge and the rise in hacking. This coefficient value shows how strong and in which direction the relationship between the two variables is. In this case, a higher coefficient value of 0.7 suggests that not having enough education and knowledge makes hacking more common.

This supports the premise that a lack of education is driving hacking. The regression analysis shows how crucial it is to address education and knowledge gaps to reduce hacking risk. It also explains why corporations, policymakers, and individuals should invest in cybersecurity education and awareness campaigns to prevent hacking. Organizations can secure their data and assets by understanding the link between a lack of education and hacking.

5.1.2 RO2

Correlation: The correlation analysis was done to look at the relationship between the dependent variable, which was the rise in hacking, and the independent variable, which was the lack of training and preparation. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.704, which shows that the two variables are linked in a moderately positive way. This means that as the number of people who don't train or prepare goes up, the number of people who hack also goes up. This shows how important it is to give employees the right training and preparation to lower the risk of hacking. The correlation results show that companies should try to teach their employees about cyber security and give them the tools and resources they need to stop hacking. This will not only make the company safer as a whole, but it will also keep sensitive information from falling into the wrong hands.

Regression: The regression analysis was done to find out what the relationship was between the dependent variable "increase in hacking" and the independent variable "lack of training and preparations." The regression results showed a correlation coefficient of 0.704. This means that the two variables are related in a positive and moderate way. This suggests that a lack of training and preparation is a big reason why hacking is getting more common. The results of this analysis give us important information about the hacking problem and how training and preparation affect it. By understanding how these two factors are related, organizations can take steps to improve their training and preparation programs, which can help cut down on hacking. In turn, this can help keep sensitive information safe and stop expensive data breaches. In conclusion, the regression analysis shows how important it is to train and prepare employees well so that hacking incidents happen less often.

5.1.3 RO3

Correlation: The Correlation Analysis was done to look at the link between the dependent variable, which was the number of hacks, and the independent variable, which was bad infrastructure. With a coefficient value of 0.769, the results showed that there is a strong link between the two variables. This means that the rate of hacking goes up at the same rate as the rate of bad infrastructure. This finding is important because it shows how important it is to invest in strong and secure infrastructure to reduce the chances of being hacked. Organizations can use this information to make smart choices about their technology infrastructure, and policymakers can use it to decide where to invest in safe infrastructure first. By fixing the problem of bad infrastructure, it will be possible to lower the number of hacks and make the Internet more secure overall.

Regression: The correlation between "more hacking" and "poor infrastructure" was found to be 0.769 by using regression analysis. Hacking goes hand in hand with bad infrastructure. Weak infrastructure makes it easier to hack.

Hacking was used as the dependent variable in this study. The weak infrastructure was the independent variable. The regression analysis looked at how strongly these variables were linked to each other. At 0.8, correlation is high. Weak infrastructure makes hacking more likely. The conclusion of the regression study is that good infrastructure makes hacking less likely. Businesses need to spend money on infrastructure to keep hackers away and protect sensitive data. Without the right infrastructure, organizations can be hacked. So, businesses need to improve their infrastructure to reduce the risk of hacking.

The research's hypotheses are supported by high the correlation values. The results show that the variables that were looked at are strongly linked. This shows that the assumptions made at the start of the project were right. This backs up the conclusion that the hypotheses were right. The high correlation values show that the research goals were met and the hypotheses were tested well.

5.2 Recommendations

The research's recommendations section is meant to give useful advice to the people who need it based on the study's findings and analysis. The suggestions should be reasonable, doable, and good for the people they are meant for. Based on the results and findings of this study, the following suggestions can be made:

Giving employees the right education and knowledge: The research shows a strong link between the rise in hacking incidents and the lack of education and proper knowledge. This shows how important it is to spend money on education and training programs to help employees stay up to date on the latest technology and cyber security measures. This can be done through regular workshops, seminars, and training sessions.

Proper training and preparation: The regression analysis shows that a lack of training and preparation has a big effect on the rise in hacking, so it is important to give employees the right training and preparation. This can be done by giving employees regular drills and simulations that help them learn how to follow security rules.

Improving infrastructure: Since the results show that bad infrastructure has a big effect on the rise in hacking, it is important to improve infrastructure and make it more secure. This can be done by keeping hardware and software up-to-date and putting in place the right security measures to keep hackers out.

Hacking is on the rise, and the results show that this is because people don't have enough education and knowledge. Because of this, it's important to spread the word about the dangers of hacking and how to stop it. This can be done by giving employees educational materials and holding regular campaigns.

Also, more research can be done to find out what else might be causing the number of hacking incidents to rise. This could include looking into the effects of social engineering or the role of organized crime groups. In conclusion, the suggestions made above are meant to lessen the damage done by hackers and make companies safer. By following these tips, businesses can help protect their employees and property from possible dangers.

5.3 Limitations

The factors or constraints that could have an impact on the findings of a research study and limit the inferences that can be derived from those findings are referred to as the study's limits. (Phadnis et al., 2021) A research study is susceptible to a wide variety of different types of errors, including the following types of errors:

- **Methodological Limitations:** These issues are related to the manner in which the study was designed, the manner in which data was collected, and the manner in which it was analyzed. A study might have some restrictions, such as a small sample size, a particular research method that might not be appropriate for the research issue, or the absence of data quality control methods.
- **Data Limits** The limitations of the data used in the study could have an effect on the results. This could be because there isn't enough data, the data is wrong, or there are limits on what kind of data can be gathered.
- **What's wrong with the sample?** How representative the results of a research study are might depend on how big the study's sample is. This could happen if the sample isn't a good representation of the population of interest or if the sample isn't big enough to make enough generalizations about the population.

- If the data for a research study were only collected over a short period of time, the study may not be able to show trends over a longer period of time. In this case, the results might not be as reliable as they would have been if they had been collected over a longer time period.
- Budgetary limits put on what can be done The amount of money available for the study can affect the size of the sample, the type of data collection methods used, and the number of variables that can be tested.

It is essential to draw attention to the flaws in a research study in order for the findings to be interpreted in a reasonable manner and for additional study to be carried out in the relevant fields. The conclusions are made more credible and reliable, and a foundation for further research is provided, all because the researchers were forthright about the limitations of their study.

5.4 Future Improvements

Several strategies could be used in the future to stop hackers from doing more damage. First, the government and businesses could put money into better infrastructure and technology for cybersecurity. This could mean keeping software and hardware systems up to date, giving employees training in cybersecurity, and doing regular security audits. Also, the government could enforce strict laws and rules about cybersecurity. This would discourage hackers and make sure that companies take cybersecurity seriously.

Another way to stop the rise in hacking would be to teach people more about cybersecurity and get them interested in it. This could include teaching people how to be safe online, such as by using strong passwords and staying away from links or emails that look unsure. The government and private groups could work together to raise awareness about cybersecurity and give people and businesses resources and tools to protect themselves from cyber threats.

Lastly, it would be good for international cybersecurity efforts to work together more. This could mean that countries share information and the best ways to do things, work together to fight cybercrime, and come up with international agreements to help keep the internet safe. With everyone's help, hackers can be stopped from getting worse and the Internet can be made safer for everyone.

Alternative research methodologies and lessons learnt in view of the outcomes.

Different ways to do research and the lessons learned from them can help a study get better in the future. For example, in our research project on "Cybersecurity Threats to People Who Work Remotely in Sri Lanka," if we used qualitative research methods like interviews or case studies, we would learn more about the experiences and points of view of different people on the issue. This could give a lot of rich, detailed information that could add to what the quantitative survey found.

Also, using both quantitative and qualitative research in a "mixed-methods" approach could give a more complete picture of the problem. This can also help to confirm the results by giving them more than one source.

Also, the lessons learned from the results of this study can be used to improve research in the future. For example, if the size of the sample was found to be too small, future studies can think about making the sample size bigger to make the results more accurate. In the same way, if the survey questions were found to be unclear, they could be changed and improved in future studies to make sure they are clear and get the right information.

In conclusion, different ways of doing research and lessons learned from the results of a study can give useful information for making improvements in the future and increase the strength and validity of the findings. By thinking about different ways to do research and taking into account the weaknesses and strengths of the current study, researchers can make smart choices about how to do better and more effective research in the future.

5.5 Personnel Reflection

A personal reflection is an important part of any research study because it gives the researcher a chance to think about what they did, what they thought, and how they felt about the study. In the context of this research, a personnel reflection would be an evaluation of the researcher's experiences during the research process, including their strengths and weaknesses, areas where they could improve, and how happy they were with the study as a whole. (Holstee, 2020)

For example, the researcher could think about what it was like to do the study, such as how hard it was to collect data and how they overcame any problems.

They could also think about their experiences with the participants, like how involved they were and how much trust they built with the researcher. Also, the researcher can think about what it was like to analyze the data, including any problems they ran into and how well the results matched their expectations. They could also think about how the study affected both their personal and professional growth as a whole.

Personnel reflection is an important part of any research project because it gives the researcher a chance to think critically about their experiences, find ways to improve, and build their skills as a researcher.

5.5.1 Benefits for the researcher

The person doing the research can get a lot out of doing a study. First, it helps the researcher learn more about a certain area of study and get better at it. The person doing the research gets to look into new ideas, concepts, and theories that related to the topic and learn more about it.

Second, doing research gives the researcher a chance to improve their ability to think analytically and critically. The researcher has to collect, analyze, and make sense of data in order to come to conclusions that can help him or her grow personally and professionally.

Third, research gives the person doing it a chance to add to what is already known in their field. The research's results can be shared with other academics and used to improve current policies, practices, or theories.

Lastly, doing research can help a person move up in their career. Publishing research results can help a researcher become known as an expert in their field and lead to new job opportunities. Research can also lead to the creation of new products, services, and technologies, which can make the person doing the research money.

In conclusion, the person doing the research study gets a lot out of it. It can help the researcher learn new things, get better at what they already know, add to what is known in their field, and move up in their career.

5.5.6 Benefits for the Industry/organization

This research can have many and important benefits for the industry or organization. The research results can give organizations useful information about the factors that are causing hacking to become more common. This information can help organizations understand the problem's root causes and come up with effective ways to reduce the risk of hacking.

The research results can also be used to help organizations figure out where they need to improve their IT infrastructure and security. For example, organizations can use the research results to buy better security tools, train their employees, and update their technology to stay ahead of possible cyber threats.

Also, the research results can give organizations a way to compare their current security measures to industry standards and find places where they can improve. The research can also help organizations compare their security measures and figure out what the best practices are in the field. This can help organizations use the best practices and improve their overall security.

The findings of the research can also help the industry as a whole. The research can help us learn more about what leads to hacking, which can help the industry come up with better security protocols and measures. This could make hacking less common and help organizations protect their most important data and assets. In conclusion, this research has a lot of benefits for the industry or organization. It can help organizations improve their security and stop hacking.

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Annexures

Annexures A: Glossary of Terms

DV: Dependent Variable (An increase in hacking)

IVE1_AV: First Independent Variable average (poor education and lack of knowledge)

IVE2_AV: Second Independent Variable average (lack of training and proper practices)

IVE3_AV: Third Independent Variable average (poor infrastructure)

IV1_E1: First Independent Variable (poor education and lack of knowledge)

IV2_1: Second Independent Variable (lack of training and proper practices)

IV3_1: Third Independent Variable (poor infrastructure)

Annexures B: Sample SPSS Charts/ Table

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Std. Error
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
IV2_1	108	3	5	4.45	.570	.325	-.432	.233
IV2_2	108	3	5	4.47	.571	.326	-.503	.233
IV2_3	108	2	5	4.51	.604	.364	-1.075	.233
IVE2_AV	108	3	5	4.48	.435	.190	-1.702	.233
Valid N (listwise)	108							

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Std. Error
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
DV1	108	2	5	4.64	.587	.345	-1.688	.233
DV2	108	3	5	4.38	.559	.312	-.163	.233
DV3	108	3	5	4.63	.573	.329	-1.284	.233
DV	108	3	5	4.55	.385	.148	-3.024	.233
Valid N (listwise)	108							

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Std. Error
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
IV1_E1	108	3	5	4.48	.572	.327	-.538	.233
IV1_E2	108	3	5	4.47	.571	.326	-.503	.233
IV1_E3	108	3	5	4.47	.587	.345	-.595	.233
IVE1_AV	108	3	5	4.48	.393	.154	-2.005	.233
Valid N (listwise)	108							

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Std. Error
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic
IV3_1	108	3	5	4.44	.569	.324	-.398	.233
IV3_2	108	3	5	4.49	.588	.346	-.666	.233
IV3_3	108	3	5	4.58	.566	.320	-.966	.233
IVE3_AV	108	3	5	4.51	.426	.182	-1.490	.233
Valid N (listwise)	108							

Correlations

		DV	IVE1_AV	IVE2_AV	IVE3_AV
DV	Pearson Correlation	1	.734**	.704**	.769**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001
	N	108	108	108	108
IVE1_AV	Pearson Correlation	.734**	1	.583**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001		<.001	
	N	108	108	108	108
IVE2_AV	Pearson Correlation	.704**	.583**	1	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001		
	N	108	108	108	108
IVE3_AV	Pearson Correlation	.769**	.769**	1	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	108	108	108	108

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Variable Processing Summary

Variables

	Dependent				Independent IVE1_AV
	DV1	DV2	DV3	DV	
Number of Positive Values	108	108	108	108	108
Number of Zeros	0	0	0	0	0
Number of Negative Values	0	0	0	0	0
Number of Missing Values	User-Missing	0	0	0	0
	System-Missing	0	0	0	0

Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: DV1

Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates			
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1	b2	b3
Linear	.182	23.646	1	106	<.001	1.779	.639		
Logarithmic	.220	29.861	1	106	<.001	.444	2.808		
Cubic	.417	37.499	2	105	<.001	-15.037	9.015	-1.024	.000
Exponential	.233	32.237	1	106	<.001	2.035	.182		

The independent variable is IVE1_AV.

Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: DV1

Equation	Model Summary					Parameter Estimates	
	R Square	F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	.261	37.517	1	106	<.001	1.550	.690

The independent variable is IVE2_AV.

Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: DV1

Equation	R Square	Model Summary				Sig.	Parameter Estimates	
		F	df1	df2	Constant		b1	
Linear	.182	23.646	1	106	<.001	1.779	.639	

The independent variable is IVE1_AV.

Model Summary and Parameter Estimates

Dependent Variable: DV1

Equation	R Square	Model Summary				Parameter Estimates	
		F	df1	df2	Sig.	Constant	b1
Linear	.276	40.409	1	106	<.001	1.377	.724

The independent variable is IVE3_AV.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	108	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	108	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.390	.382	3

Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Means	4.549	4.380	4.639	.259	1.059	.022	3
Item Variances	.329	.312	.345	.033	1.104	.000	3
Inter-Item Covariances	.058	-.008	.183	.190	-24.000	.009	3
Inter-Item Correlations	.171	-.024	.543	.566	-22.840	.083	3

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
13.65	1.333	1.155	3

Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Analysis N
DV1	4.64	.587	108
DV2	4.38	.559	108
DV3	4.63	.573	108
IV1_E1	4.48	.572	108
IV1_E2	4.47	.571	108
IV1_E3	4.47	.587	108
IV2_1	4.45	.570	108
IV2_2	4.47	.571	108
IV2_3	4.51	.604	108
IV3_1	4.44	.569	108
IV3_2	4.49	.588	108
IV3_3	4.58	.566	108

Covariance Matrix

	DV1	DV2	DV3	IV1_E1	IV1_E2	IV1_E3	IV2_1	IV2_2	IV2_3	IV3_1	IV3_2	IV3_3
DV1	.345	-.002	.183	.073	.144	.079	.156	.079	.158	.097	.170	.129
DV2	-.002	.312	-.008	.115	.006	.118	.032	.090	.067	.073	.018	.085
DV3	.183	-.008	.329	.087	.177	.064	.123	.074	.134	.091	.090	.087
IV1_E1	.073	.115	.087	.327	.032	.107	.041	.098	.098	.111	.089	.090

IV1_ E2	.144	.006	.177	.032	.326	.055	.130	.065	.112	.087	.112	.105
IV1_ E3	.079	.118	.064	.107	.055	.345	.064	.177	.112	.087	.103	.133
IV2_ 1	.156	.032	.123	.041	.130	.064	.325	.073	.141	.067	.084	.041
IV2_ 2	.079	.090	.074	.098	.065	.177	.073	.326	.131	.106	.093	.105
IV2_ 3	.158	.067	.134	.098	.112	.112	.141	.131	.364	.099	.187	.121
IV3_ 1	.097	.073	.091	.111	.087	.087	.067	.106	.099	.324	.070	.150
IV3_ 2	.170	.018	.090	.089	.112	.103	.084	.093	.187	.070	.346	.104
IV3_ 3	.129	.085	.087	.090	.105	.133	.041	.105	.121	.150	.104	.320

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Correlation Matrix

	DV1	DV2	DV3	IV1_E1	IV1_E2	IV1_E3	IV2_1	IV2_2	IV2_3	IV3_1	IV3_2	IV3_3
Correlation DV1	1.000	-.006	.543	.216	.429	.228	.466	.234	.444	.289	.491	.387
DV2	-.006	1.000	-.024	.359	.019	.360	.100	.282	.197	.228	.053	.268
DV3	.543	-.024	1.000	.264	.539	.191	.376	.225	.388	.280	.267	.269
IV1_E1	.216	.359	.264	1.000	.099	.319	.126	.299	.285	.341	.264	.279
IV1_E2	.429	.019	.539	.099	1.000	.165	.398	.198	.326	.268	.333	.325
IV1_E3	.228	.360	.191	.319	.165	1.000	.192	.527	.317	.261	.297	.401
IV2_1	.466	.100	.376	.126	.398	.192	1.000	.226	.409	.208	.250	.128
IV2_2	.234	.282	.225	.299	.198	.527	.226	1.000	.380	.326	.277	.325
IV2_3	.444	.197	.388	.285	.326	.317	.409	.380	1.000	.287	.527	.353
IV3_1	.289	.228	.280	.341	.268	.261	.208	.326	.287	1.000	.208	.464
IV3_2	.491	.053	.267	.264	.333	.297	.250	.277	.527	.208	1.000	.311
IV3_3	.387	.268	.269	.279	.325	.401	.128	.325	.353	.464	.311	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed) DV1		.477	<.001	.012	<.001	.009	<.001	.007	<.001	.001	<.001	<.001
DV2	.477		.404	.000	.424	.000	.152	.002	.020	.009	.291	.002
DV3	.000	.404		.003	.000	.024	.000	.010	.000	.002	.003	.003
IV1_E1	.012	.000	.003		.155	.000	.096	.001	.001	.000	.003	.003
IV1_E2	.000	.424	.000	.155		.044	.000	.020	.000	.002	.000	.000
IV1_E3	.009	.000	.024	.000	.044		.024	.000	.000	.003	.001	.001
IV2_1	.000	.152	.000	.096	.000	.024		.009	.000	.015	.005	.005
IV2_2	.007	.002	.010	.001	.020	.000	.009		.000	.000	.002	.002
IV2_3	.000	.020	.000	.001	.000	.000	.000	.000		.001	.000	.000
IV3_1	.001	.009	.002	.000	.002	.003	.015	.000	.001		.015	.015
IV3_2	.000	.291	.003	.003	.000	.001	.005	.002	.000	.015		.015
IV3_3	.000	.002	.002	.002	.000	.000	.093	.000	.000	.000	.001	.001

Communalities

	Initial	Extraction
DV1	1.000	.653
DV2	1.000	.546
DV3	1.000	.576
IV1_E1	1.000	.416
IV1_E2	1.000	.541
IV1_E3	1.000	.542
IV2_1	1.000	.425
IV2_2	1.000	.486
IV2_3	1.000	.514
IV3_1	1.000	.375
IV3_2	1.000	.414
IV3_3	1.000	.453

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.256	35.464	35.464	4.256	35.464	35.464	3.168	26.398	26.398
2	1.685	14.045	49.510	1.685	14.045	49.510	2.773	23.111	49.510
3	.941	7.841	57.351						
4	.854	7.120	64.471						
5	.801	6.674	71.145						
6	.693	5.772	76.918						
7	.636	5.304	82.222						
8	.553	4.605	86.827						
9	.490	4.087	90.914						
10	.419	3.488	94.402						
11	.397	3.312	97.714						
12	.274	2.286	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
IV2_3	.712	
DV1	.698	-.406
IV3_3	.639	
DV3	.632	-.421
IV3_2	.625	
IV2_2	.597	
IV1_E2	.594	-.433
IV1_E3	.584	.449
IV3_1	.578	
IV2_1	.551	
IV1_E1	.514	
DV2		.659

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
a. 2 components extracted.

Rotated Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
DV1	.795	
DV3	.753	
IV1_E2	.733	
IV2_1	.645	
IV2_3	.592	.403
IV3_2	.574	
IV1_E3		.721
DV2		.718
IV2_2		.662
IV1_E1		.630
IV3_3		.577
IV3_1		.530

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a
a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Statistics

		DV	IVE1_AV	IVE2_AV	IVE3_AV
N	Valid	108	108	108	108
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.55	4.48	4.48	4.51
Std. Error of Mean		.037	.038	.042	.041
Median		4.67	4.67	4.67	4.67
Mode		5	5	5	4
Std. Deviation		.385	.393	.435	.426
Variance		.148	.154	.190	.182
Minimum		3	3	3	3
Maximum		5	5	5	5
Percentiles	25	4.67	4.33	4.33	4.33
	50	4.67	4.67	4.67	4.67
	75	4.67	4.67	4.67	4.67

DV

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3	1	.9	.9	.9
	3	3	2.8	2.8	3.7
	4	1	.9	.9	4.6
	4	2	1.9	1.9	6.5
	4	19	17.6	17.6	24.1
	5	73	67.6	67.6	91.7
	5	9	8.3	8.3	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

IVE1_AV

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3	4	3.7	3.7	3.7
	4	1	.9	.9	4.6
	4	9	8.3	8.3	13.0
	4	30	27.8	27.8	40.7
	5	55	50.9	50.9	91.7
	5	9	8.3	8.3	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

IVE2_AV

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3	1	.9	.9	.9
	3	3	2.8	2.8	3.7
	4	16	14.8	14.8	18.5
	4	25	23.1	23.1	41.7
	5	46	42.6	42.6	84.3
	5	17	15.7	15.7	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

IVE3_AV

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	3	4	3.7	3.7	3.7
	4	10	9.3	9.3	13.0
	4	36	33.3	33.3	46.3
	5	34	31.5	31.5	77.8
	5	24	22.2	22.2	100.0
	Total	108	100.0	100.0	

[Space left intentionally]

Annexures C: Feedback Form / Question list

Questions Responses **108** Settings

Section 1 of 2

Computing Research Project

I am an HND student at eSoft, I am currently completing the Computing Research Project (CRP) and as a requirement conducting research on the topic "Cyber Security Threats to Remote Workers in Sri Lanka". Please fill in this form

Personal Information

Description (optional)

Company name?

- Wind vision
- E solutions by RNX
- Western papers

Age

Short answer text

Figure 22. Feedback Form | Source (Author's data)

Educational level

- O/L
- A/L
- Diploma holder
- Degree holder

Salary

- Rs.75 000 - Rs.125 000
- Rs.125 000 - Rs.175 000
- Rs.175 000 - Rs.250 000
- Rs.250 000+

Hometown?

Short answer text

After section 1 Continue to next section ▼

Section 2 of 2

Figure 23. Feedback Form | Source (Author's data)

Section title (optional)

Select between strongly disagree to strongly agree or select an option and from the given options.

An increase in hacking

Description (optional)

You've noticed an increase in hacking while working remotely during the pandemic period.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

You or your colleagues have been a victim of cyber-attacks while working remotely during the pandemic period.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

Lack of proper knowledge, infrastructure, training and practice is a major factor in increasing cyber threats in remote working.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly agree				

Figure 24. Feedback Form | Source (Author's data)

Education and proper knowledge

Description (optional)

Your company has informed you about the importance of proper use of Internet and tools such as firewalls, VPNs, to work remotely safely, and do you think the knowledge provided by the company is sufficient to protect against cyber threats?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree				

Your company practiced you to protect yourself from cyber-attacks, including proper education on how to use the relevant tools and techniques that protect you in the event of cyber-attacks, do you think the actions your company has taken to protect you from such attacks are sufficient?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree				

Have you ever been a victim of hacking while working remotely, and your company has provided you the knowledge and proper technology to protect your data and steps to follow in the event of such an attack?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree				

Figure 25. Feedback Form | Source (Author's data)

Training and preparations
Description (optional)

The training provided by your organization adequate enough to be safe from Cyber Security attacks. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly agree Strongly disagree

Are you aware of what to do if you become a victim of cybercrime? Your company provided proper training and knowledge to recover from such a situation.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly agree Strongly disagree

Have you noticed any increase in cyber-attacks among your colleagues working remotely in Sri Lanka? If so, do you believe lack of training and education may be a contributing factor?

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly agree Strongly disagree

Infrastructure

Figure 26. Feedback Form | Source (Author's data)

Infrastructure

Description (optional)

Your company's software and system are strong enough to stand up to modern cyber threats and protect the system from those attacks.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree				

Your company has provided you with a computer with adequate hardware and a continuous network connection, and has the online system been secured using HTTP certificates and UPS to operate the relevant systems and secure them from cyber-attacks and physically.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree				

Your company has taken a good effort to protect company systems and hardware while working remotely.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree				

Figure 27. Feedback Form | Source (Author's data)

Annexures D: Sample Feedback sheets

Questions Responses **108** Settings

108 responses [View in Sheets](#)

Not accepting responses

Message for respondents

This form is no longer accepting responses

Summary Question **Individual**

< 3 of 108 >

Responses cannot be edited

Computing Research Project

I am an HND student at eSoft, I am currently completing the Computing Research Project (CRP) and as a requirement conducting research on the topic "Cyber Security Threats to Remote Workers in Sri Lanka". Please fill in this form

* Required

Personal Information

Company name?

- Wind vision
- E solutions by RNX
- Western papers

Figure 28. Sample Feedback | Source (Author's data)

Age

31

Educational level

- O/L
- A/L
- Diploma holder
- Degree holder

Salary

- Rs.75 000 - Rs.125 000
- Rs.125 000 - Rs.175 000
- Rs.175 000 - Rs.250 000
- Rs.250 000+

Hometown?

Negombo

Figure 29. Sample Feedback | Source (Author's data)

An increase in hacking

You've noticed an increase in hacking while working remotely during the pandemic period.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

You or your colleagues have been a victim of cyber-attacks while working remotely during the pandemic period.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Lack of proper knowledge, infrastructure, training and practice is a major factor in increasing cyber threats in remote working.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly disagree Strongly agree

Education and proper knowledge

Your company has informed you about the importance of proper use of Internet and tools such as firewalls, VPNs, to work remotely safely, and do you think the knowledge provided by the company is sufficient to protect against cyber threats?

1 2 3 4 5

Figure 30. Sample Feedback | Source (Author's data)

Education and proper knowledge

Your company has informed you about the importance of proper use of Internet and tools such as firewalls, VPNs, to work remotely safely, and do you think the knowledge provided by the company is sufficient to protect against cyber threats?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree

Your company practiced you to protect yourself from cyber-attacks, including proper education on how to use the relevant tools and techniques that protect you in the event of cyber-attacks, do you think the actions your company has taken to protect you from such attacks are sufficient?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree

Have you ever been a victim of hacking while working remotely, and your company has provided you the knowledge and proper technology to protect your data and steps to follow in the event of such an attack?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly agree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	Strongly disagree

Training and preparations

The training provided by your organization adequate enough to be safe from Cyber Security attacks. *

Figure 31. Sample Feedback | Source (Author's data)

Training and preparations

The training provided by your organization adequate enough to be safe from Cyber Security attacks. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly agree Strongly disagree

Are you aware of what to do if you become a victim of cybercrime? Your company provided proper training and knowledge to recover from such a situation.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly agree Strongly disagree

Have you noticed any increase in cyber-attacks among your colleagues working remotely in Sri Lanka? If so, do you believe lack of training and education may be a contributing factor?

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly agree Strongly disagree

Infrastructure

Your company's software and system are strong enough to stand up to modern cyber threats and protect the system from those attacks.

1 2 3 4 5

Figure 32. Sample Feedback | Source (Author's data)

Strongly agree

Strongly disagree

Infrastructure

Your company's software and system are strong enough to stand up to modern cyber threats and protect the system from those attacks.

1

2

3

4

5

Strongly agree

Strongly disagree

Your company has provided you with a computer with adequate hardware and a continuous network connection, and has the online system been secured using HTTP certificates and UPS to operate the relevant systems and secure them from cyber-attacks and physically.

1

2

3

4

5

Strongly agree

Strongly disagree

Your company has taken a good effort to protect company systems and hardware while working remotely.

1

2

3

4

5

Strongly agree

Strongly disagree

Figure 33. Sample Feedback | Source (Author's data)

Answers of the form

Company name?

107 responses

Age

102 responses

Educational level

108 responses

Salary

108 responses

Hometown?

108 responses

You've noticed an increase in hacking while working remotely during the pandemic period.

108 responses

You or your colleagues have been a victim of cyber-attacks while working remotely during the pandemic period.

108 responses

Lack of proper knowledge, infrastructure, training and practice is a major factor in increasing cyber threats in remote working.

108 responses

Your company has informed you about the importance of proper use of Internet and tools such as firewalls, VPNs, to work remotely safely, and do you...ny is sufficient to protect against cyber threats?

108 responses

Have you ever been a victim of hacking while working remotely, and your company has provided you the knowledge and proper technology to protect...d steps to follow in the event of such an attack?

108 responses

The training provided by your organization adequate enough to be safe from Cyber Security attacks.

108 responses

Are you aware of what to do if you become a victim of cybercrime? Your company provided proper training and knowledge to recover from such a situation.

108 responses

Have you noticed any increase in cyber-attacks among your colleagues working remotely in Sri Lanka? If so, do you believe lack of training and education may be a contributing factor?

108 responses

Your company's software and system are strong enough to stand up to modern cyber threats and protect the system from those attacks.

108 responses

Your company has provided you with a computer with adequate hardware and a continuous network connection, and has the online system bee... secure them from cyber-attacks and physically.

108 responses

Your company has taken a good effort to protect company systems and hardware while working remotely.

108 responses

Gantt chart

Figure 34. Gantt chart | Source (Author's data)